

MSCR

Metadata Schema & Crosswalk Registry

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

MSCR is a registry to support research data management, which allows registered users and communities to create, register and version meta data schemas and crosswalks with resolvable identifiers. The published content can be searched, browsed and downloaded without restrictions. It also provides an API to facilitate the management of contents and transformation of data from one schema to another via registered crosswalks.

The key focus of MSCR are:

Providing a registry for existing schemas and crosswalks, creating a tool for defining and describing crosswalks between existing schemas, and **facilitating the transformation of (meta)data documents** using crosswalks created with the MSCR.

The implemented MSCR service contributes to the FAIRness of research related data by making its metadata (schemas) more findable and accessible, it promotes discoverability, accessibility and re-usability of crosswalks through uniquely identified, uniform and structured mapping sets, and allows crosswalk specifications to be made directly interoperable through artefacts generated for crosswalk operationalisation.

Functionalities

1. Registration of schemas and crosswalks in multiple formats. The supported formats currently are CSV, XSD, JSON Schema, RDFS, SHACL, OWL, SKOS. ENUM and PDF for schemas and SSSOM, Simple Table, XSLT and PDF for crosswalks.
2. Basic content management support like resolvable handles, rich metadata, versioning and provenance information.
3. Crosswalk Editor for visually creating crosswalks between metadata schemas
4. Generation of executable versions of crosswalks (e.g. XSLT) to support (meta)data transformation.
5. Content creation and management through APIs.
6. Integration with Data Type Registry (DTR) to provide custom data types for the metadata schemas and Vocabulary Service to map attribute values to specific vocabularies.
7. Notification service to allow users to subscribe to content changes.
8. Integration with B2Access AAI for easy authentication.

Impact

The MSCR facilitates interoperability between information systems on a semantic and technical levels through discoverable, accessible and actionable schemas and crosswalks. By providing an easy to use GUI for creating crosswalks, the MSCR attracts users currently relying on project specific solutions for implementing (meta)data mappings. The MSCR works on data schemas, vocabularies and other semantic artefacts and encourages organisations and individual researchers to share, use and reuse crosswalks in a way that can make previously hard to find interoperability work in research related workflows visible in a uniform way (FAIRification).

Discover the
MSCR Service